

ETHNOPEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR DEVELOPING THE ECOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article examines the development of environmental competence of school teachers as a pedagogical problem, environmental, social and economic, as well as legal aspects of sustainable development, the possibility of analyzing the principles and improving the mechanisms of environmental competence by scientists.*

Keywords: *ecological culture, ecological literacy, ecological competence, ethnopedagogy, ethnopedagogic approach and ecological value.*

Introduction

In recent years, significant efforts have been made in our country to address ecological challenges through education by changing schoolteachers' attitudes towards the environment, nature, and its resources. Additionally, initiatives have been implemented to cultivate students' culture of utilizing natural resources sustainably and to establish regulatory foundations for fostering resource conservation within the school education system. ¹Increasing "ecological awareness among the population and nurturing a sense of love and responsibility for nature in the hearts of the younger generation" has been identified as a priority. As a result, the pedagogical opportunities for developing schoolteachers' ecological competence are expanding.

Ecological culture represents the pinnacle of an individual's educational and professional qualifications, reflecting positive traits of human morality at the highest level of spirituality. Amidst the current processes of globalization, humanity is facing pressing ecological issues, making the enhancement of ecological literacy and competence within the educational system an essential requirement. Teachers' ecological competence plays a pivotal role in instilling a responsible attitude towards the environment among students, fostering the principles of nature conservation, and promoting sustainable development.

The ethnopedagogical approach to ecological education contributes to cultivating ecological awareness and knowledge among teachers based on national values and respect for nature. Ethnopedagogy, encompassing educational and upbringing methods derived from the rich historical and cultural heritage of the people, is recognized as an effective approach to shaping teachers' ecological competence. This method enables teachers to convey the concept of harmony between national values and nature to students while educating them about ecological literacy.

Through school education, students can be instilled with ecological values inspired by the customs and traditions of our people concerning nature, including national celebrations. This approach encourages students to preserve nature and participate actively in addressing ecological problems.

From this perspective, integrating national values into the content of ecological education and preparing teachers using an ethnopedagogical approach are crucial in the process of enhancing

schoolteachers' ecological competence. By employing this approach, teachers can develop ecological culture and responsibility among students, equipping them with the necessary knowledge and skills to actively participate in solving ecological issues.

Analysis of Literature Related to the Topic

The relevance of enhancing ecological literacy lies in the need to protect the natural environment, ecosystems, and stability of our country while promoting ecological culture among the population. This includes fostering "green skills" among all social groups, particularly school students, and effectively implementing methodologies aimed at addressing real-life ecological issues. Developing ecological literacy and competence in general secondary education schools has been the focus of various researchers, including E. Turdiqulov, P. Berdanova, N. Bozorova, N. Mirzayeva, R. Djurayev, N. Isakulova, A. Malikova, Sh. Otaboyev, A. Ergashev, N. Nishonova, X. Norboyev, M. Aliqulova, and S. Mamashokirov. Their studies have explored the content of ecological education, strategies for developing ecological culture among students, interdisciplinary methods for fostering ecological thinking in schoolchildren, and approaches to enhancing ecological literacy.

M. Rakhimqulova's research emphasizes fostering ecological values in extracurricular activities, while N. Egamberdiyeva investigates the scientific-pedagogical foundations of moral upbringing influenced by the environment (using pedagogical colleges as an example). N. Bozorova examines the pedagogical foundations for enhancing ecological culture among students, and M. Aliqulova explores the pedagogical conditions for incorporating the ecological perspectives of Central Asian scholars into natural science lessons. Similarly, N. Meliboyev's work focuses on preparing future teachers to deliver ecological education during professional development courses.

In addition, T. Kapustina, E. Zhuk, and R. Simonakhina have conducted research on the development of ecological competence through the teaching of courses "Introduction to Specialty". They argue that ecological competence, as a fundamental component of human culture, is closely linked to addressing complex ecological challenges and serves as a prerequisite for sustainable lifestyles and consistent development.

The process of enhancing ecological competences aims to instill in individuals a responsible attitude towards the environment and health. This involves fostering a system of scientific and practical knowledge, skills, value orientations, and behavioral patterns that align with ideological relationships and contribute to sustainable ecological practices.

These scholarly works highlight the importance of ecological literacy and competence as essential tools for addressing modern environmental challenges, particularly within the educational context, where schoolteachers play a pivotal role in shaping students' ecological awareness and values.

O. Magntorn focuses on the development of ecological literacy through the study of nature. His research addresses the concept of "knowing nature" and its role in environmental education. He defines studying nature as understanding organisms and their interrelations, integrating material related to the flow of energy and matter within ecosystems, and recognizing their connection to the environment.

N. Roksan, J. Kayser, H. Bogner, and M. Wilson emphasize that skills, motivations, beliefs, and perceptions must be closely linked to ecological influences. They argue that the primary factors influencing ecological behavior are largely connected to an individual's level of expertise.

According to them, no directed influence is expected between these factors unless the person's competence level plays a central role.

Figure 1. Key Indicators of Ecological Competence

Analyzing the components of ecology, we conclude that ecological competence is composed of motivational, cognitive, creative, and operational components. It is important to consider the stages of ecological competence development, which include unconscious incompetence, conscious incompetence, conscious competence, and unconscious competence. These stages must be understood logically.

I. Wagner asserts that an ethnopedagogical approach in ecological education helps foster value development in adolescents. Such an approach forms the basis for fostering love for nature, aesthetic appreciation, and an understanding of human connections with the environment, essential for creative activities aimed at conserving the natural world.

N. Roshen's analysis highlights that understanding cognitive and motivational approaches specific to ecology plays a crucial role in the development of ecological behavior. An effective model of ecological competence supports promoting ecological behavior.

Studies by P. Barthelmess, M. Schuz, R. Fuchs, D. Kucera, M. Prandini show that recognizing ecological boundaries and understanding the roles of human activities as agents of environmental change contribute to self-responsibility and value systems. These studies, based on the experiences of students in South Korea, Switzerland, and the Czech Republic, demonstrate that awareness of ecological limits fosters responsibility toward the planet's future.

In conclusion, when approaching the concept of "ecological competence," it is essential to recognize the interconnections between religious, social, and philosophical traditions with ecological understanding. Ecological competence must be built on a foundation of scientific understanding, along with philosophical perspectives on sustainable living and nature's elements. Learning about ecosystems and nature leads to ecological literacy, highlighting the importance of observing environmental changes caused by human activities, whether direct or indirect.

Sustainable development is not just a goal but a result of cultivating the ability to understand and connect with nature, and to actively engage in its preservation.

Ecological Competence and the Role of Ethnopedagogy in Educating Teachers

When we speak of "ecological competence," we refer to the development of specific ecological knowledge and thinking among school teachers, aimed at fostering a responsible relationship with the environment (nature). This includes promoting care for both their own health and the well-being of others, as well as fostering a responsible attitude towards adopting a healthy lifestyle. The goal of developing ecological competence is to enhance teachers' ecological consciousness and culture by developing their knowledge, skills, and competencies in a way that aligns with the scientific and theoretical foundations of ecology, enabling them to maintain a responsible attitude toward the environment.

Ethnopedagogy refers to the empirical experience of ethnic groups in the upbringing and education of children (emotional and practical experience) and is concerned with moral, ethical, and aesthetic attitudes regarding family, clan, tribe, nationality, and national values. In ethnopedagogy, traditional culture, lifestyle, and family and kinship relations are considered in shaping the individual. Ethnopedagogy deals with the ethical and ecological norms of the natural and social environment, focusing on shaping attitudes toward nature and developing ecological behavior.

From the analysis, it can be concluded that ethnopedagogical knowledge becomes the foundation for ecological knowledge and skills, passing down through generations via customs, rituals, and festivals. For example, environmental awareness days like April 15 (Ecology Day), May 12 (Environmental Education Day), June 5 (World Environment Day), and other significant dates related to ecological values in our republic help foster ecological literacy and the development of students' understanding of the environment.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

In conclusion, the development of ecological competence among school teachers in both international and national educational institutions hold significant importance. Today, ecological culture, understanding the relationship with the environment, and approaching ecological issues responsibly should be fundamental skills for teachers. Incorporating ecological literacy into the curriculum and implementing methods that promote ecological thinking and behavior for both teachers and students is necessary.

Through scientific research and ethnopedagogical approaches, there is an opportunity to use both national and international experiences in forming ecological competence among school teachers. This will help teachers guide their students to responsibly approach the environment, instill skills to address ecological issues, and promote the conservation of nature. Furthermore, by celebrating national and international environmental days and promoting values related to nature, it is possible to achieve significant results in developing ecological culture.

These findings emphasize the importance of developing ecological competence to raise ecological awareness among teachers and foster ecological knowledge and skills within the educational process.

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